

CHARACTERIZATION OF POULTRY FARMING IN NIGERIA: A CASE STUDY OF TARABA STATE

D. Zahraddeen¹, I.S.R. Butswat², M. Sanusi¹ and S. A. Adamu¹

¹Animal Production Programme, School of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, P.M.B. 0248, Bauchi, Nigeria, ²National Open University of Nigeria, Jos Study Centre, Jos, Plateau State, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to characterize the poultry farming in Taraba State, Nigeria. Eight (8) Local Government Areas (LGAs) were randomly selected out of the sixteen (16) LGAs in the State. A total of fifty structured questionnaires were randomly administered to poultry farmers to collate some relevant information on the challenges facing them. The data collected were subjected to simple descriptive statistics using means and percentages to describe socio-economic activities and other information regarding the farmers. The results showed that majority (71.4%) of the farmers were within the age group of 21-40 years. Poultry enterprise in the State was mainly a business for the males, accounting for about 71.4%. The educational background of the farmers showed that 71.4% had formal and tertiary education, with few others having only secondary (25.0%) or Qur`anic (3.6%) education. However, most farmers (82.1%) had experience ranging from 1 to 10 years in the business. Poultry farming was mainly for commercial purpose (61.9%) with few others keeping/rearing poultry for consumption (33.3%) and 4.8% for prestige. About 53.6% of the farmers sell or otherwise dispose of their birds all-year round, while few others target sales during festive occasions, *Eid-el- Fitr* (21.4%) and 14.3% for Christmas. The results also revealed that farmers kept various poultry species. This was made up of 87.5% chickens, 9.4% turkeys and 3.1% guinea fowls; with 89.3% of these animals being improved breeds. Poultry keeping was mainly operated at small-scale level (46.4%) having ≤ 300 birds per farmer. This was followed by medium-sized operations; those with birds ranging from 301 to 600 birds per individual farmer (39.3%). About 14.3% of farmers practised large scale poultry production with 1201 to 1500 birds per farmer. The majority (85.7%) of farmers kept their poultry under an intensive management system. There were 10.7 and 3.6% farmers who practised the semi-intensive and extensive systems of production, respectively. Reported cases of disease incidence among farmers; fowl fox (17.6%), fowl cholera (17.6%), Gumboro (11.8%), Newcastle (23.5%), fowl typhoid (23.5%) and coccidiosis (5.9%). Most disease outbreaks (46.4%) occurred during the late wet season followed by 28.6 % in the early dry season and the late dry season with a 25.0% incidence rate. Disease outbreak was the major militating factor against poultry production. High cost of feeds as well as the cost of disease treatment was also a limiting factor in the production processes. Generally, improved management practices as well as prompt control of diseases will go a long way towards increased productivity of this species in the area.

KEY WORDS: Poultry, production, prospects, constraints

INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria, there is a general outcry of dearth of protein supply, especially of animal origin among the populace. Animal protein is one of the most important components of human meals and its consumption varies from country to country (Butswat *et al.*, 2002). In the developed countries, average per person daily intake stands at over 50 grams, while in the developing countries including Nigeria, it is only between 12 and 20 grams or 3 to 4 times lower (FAO, 1998).

Nigerians own many varieties of farm animals including poultry. Poultry ranks highest in number among the farm animals on the farm; mostly 80 – 90 % owned by small scale farmers (Idi, 2000). Poultry production is increasing very rapidly and the consumption is increasing faster than that of other kinds of meat beside beef (Bukar, 2003). The population of poultry in the country was estimated to be 104.3

million; chickens (72.4 million), pigeons (15.2 million), ducks (11.8 million), guinea fowl (4.7 million) and turkeys (0.2 million) (FDLPCS, 1992), of which most are local stocks.

Poultry are resources available to even the poorest families (Aini, 1990). It has been shown that nearly every household keeps at least one form of poultry species. Poultry have proved to be a particularly versatile group of domestic animal species that are adapted to a wide ranging climate. However, with any programme meant to improve the poultry, it is always necessary to include the local stock since they possess some innate resistance to certain local diseases in addition to a high degree of adaptability to the prevailing climatic conditions. Thus genetic improvement could be attained at a faster rate if local stocks were involved in selective breeding. The Nigerian indigenous stock are a genomic bank not adequately harnessed and there is great potential for improving and increasing local poultry numbers through small-holders for sustainable animal protein production in the country. The priority must be given to poultry because they are widely and evenly distributed all over the ecological zones of the country. There is also the possibility of a high turn-over rate in poultry production and most important poultry have a shorter generation interval than most farm animal species.

Poultry production has developed into a commercial enterprise involving thousands of birds. Large poultry units have replaced small ones, as more efficient strains of birds, balanced rations, intensive housing and better poultry equipment came into use (Oluyemi and Roberts, 1988; Obioha, 1992). These developments led to the spread of different strains of birds world-wide. In Taraba State, the study area, not much is known about the species composition of poultry reared and the constraints hampering efficient poultry farming. Therefore, this study was designed to characterize the poultry farming in the State with the hope of suggesting areas for improvement in their husbandry for better quality egg and meat production.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Location

Taraba State, the study area, apart from being the state capital and headquarters of Jalingo Local Government Area, is also the urban centre in the State. It lies between latitudes 6° 25' and 9° 30' north and between longitudes 9° 30' and 11° 45' east. It has an estimated land area of about 54,428 square kilometres. The State borders to the west by Gombe and Plateau, south west by Benue, northeast by Adamawa States. An international boundary on the east separates the State from Republic of Cameroon. The topography is largely made up of undulating plains and rising hills. It is transverse by many rivers, the major one being River Benue which rises from the highlands of the Cameroon and flows southwards to join the River Niger (Kowal and Knabe, 1972).

Climate

The State has a total human population of more than 2.3 million (NPC, 2006). The society is mainly agrarian. The climate is suitable for agriculture. It is characterised by two distinct seasons (dry and wet). The wet season usually starts from April to end in October while the dry season is from November to March. April is the hottest month of the year with a mean maximum temperature of about 28°C. The average yearly rainfall is about 1,350 mm. The mean monthly hours of sunshine is highest in December and lowest in August. The mean relative humidity is highest in August and lowest in February (TED, 1992).

Sampling technique

The State has a total of sixteen (16) LGAs. Eight (8) LGAs were randomly sampled and used for the study. Twenty eight (28) structured questionnaires were randomly administered to these LGAs to ensure that each location was given equal chance. The questionnaires were distributed to poultry farmers in the area. The importance of this technique is based on the assertion of Loveday (1970), who described the random sampling process as a repetitive operation that in a simple trial may result in any one a number of possible outcomes each determined by chance.

Data collection

The main tool used for data collection was a structured questionnaire, which was supplemented by oral interviews at the time of administration. The information required from the farmers were their socio-

economic background, poultry species composition, management practices, disease incidence, and constraints to poultry keeping, among others.

Data analysis

The data generated from this study were subjected to simple descriptive statistics (means and percentages), which were used to describe farmers' socio-economic characteristics and other relevant information, as described by Humburg (1977).

RESULTS

Table 1 shows data on socio-economic characteristics of poultry farmers in Taraba State. The results showed that majority of the farmers (71.4%) are within the age-range group of 21 – 40 years. There were 10.7 and 17.9% farmers within the age groups of 0 – 20 and ≥ 41 years, respectively. The farmers are predominately males (71.4%). The results also showed that most farmers (71.4%) had tertiary education, with others having 25.0 and 3.6% for secondary and Qur'anic educations, respectively. It was also revealed that most farmers (82.1%) had experience ranging from 1 to 10 years. This was followed by those with 11 – 20 years' experience, accounting for 10.7%. There were two farmers (3.6%) having experience of 21 to 30 and 31 to 40 years, respectively. The results showed that majority (61.9%) of the farmers reared poultry for sale. About 33.3 and 4.8% raised birds specifically for consumption and prestige, respectively. There were 53.6% of farmers that sold or otherwise disposed their poultry all-year round with few others during festive seasons; *Eid-el- Fitr* (21.4%), Christmas (14.3%), *Eid-el- Kabir* (3.6%), Easter (3.6%) and wedding and ceremonies (3.6%).

Data on poultry species, breed type, flock size and management system are presented in Table 2. The results showed that chickens (87.5%) were the predominate species reared by farmers in the locality; with turkey and guinea fowl farmers having 9.4 and 3.1%, respectively. Most farmers (89.3%) stocked their poultry houses with exotic (improved) breeds. The flock size structure revealed that most farmers (46.4%) are operating the business at small-scale level with ≤ 300 birds per farmer. This was followed by those with 301 – 600 birds represented by 39.3%. The least was for those who practised the large-scale production system (14.3%) having up to 1201 – 1500 birds per individual. However, most farmers (85.7%) reared birds using improved housing conditions (intensive management or complete confinement of birds), then followed by those (10.7%) who raised poultry under the semi-intensive system, where animals are given some hours to stay outdoor before taken back to their pens. There were only 3.6% of the farmers who managed birds using the traditional method of poultry rearing; the extensive system, where birds are allowed to fend for themselves.

Information on disease incidence, season of outbreak and constraints to poultry production are shown in Table 3. The results revealed that most of the farmers (60.7%) encountered one or more disease outbreaks in the last five years. The diseases reported included fowl fox, fowl cholera, Gumboro disease, Newcastle disease, fowl typhoid and coccidiosis; with incidence rates of 17.6, 17.6, 11.8, 23.5, 23.5 and 5.9%, respectively. Out of the outbreaks only 69.2% of the farmers subjected the diseases to confirmatory test to ascertain their true occurrence on the farms. These outbreaks occurred mainly (46.4%) during the late wet season (July – September). The early dry season (October – December) had an outbreak rate of 28.6%. This was followed by the late dry season (January - March) having 25.0% outbreak rate. However, there was no disease outbreak reported during the early wet season (April – June). Poultry farmers showed that the cost of feeds, economic losses associated with disease outbreaks, the cost of drugs/medications, inadequate capital, inadequate veterinary personnel, inadequate credit facility and an irregular electricity supply were among the many constraints hampering the smooth running of poultry business in the State; values being 30.8, 20.0, 16.9, 7.7, 7.7, 6.2, 6.2 and 4.6%, respectively.

DISCUSSION

The socio-economic characteristics and other indices of poultry farming in the State showed that poultry production is mainly a business for the young males. This means that the male farmers are more willing to engage in poultry farming or other profitable ventures than the female ones. This also implies that the males are more willing to take farming risk than their female counterparts. This was similarly observed by Utomakili and Inwalowu (1993) that the young people are generally more able and willing to take risk in expectation of profit and older ones are risk averse. The differential educational background of the

farmers and age group usually account for differential ability to evaluate and manage farm risk, which in turn determines to a large extent the overall success of the farming enterprise. The larger proportion of the farmers had tertiary education which is an indication that positive changes on improved production systems are likely to be warmly-accepted as compared to farmers who have low level of education. This agrees with the findings of Obibuaka (1993) who stated that education is not only an important determinant of adoption of new technologies, but also a tool for successful implementation of the innovation for profitability.

Majority of the farmers had experience ranging from 1 to 10 years, which means that poultry farming is a newly discovered 'gold mine' in the study area. This means management and other costs of production will be optimally utilized by the farmers to enhance their income generation, which subsequently brings sustainability to animal protein production. Most farmers keep poultry in order to dispose of or sale them when fully mature and at high market value. This implies that poultry keeping is solely for commercial purpose in the State. This is in close agreement with the reports of Jull (1984) who stated that first-hand knowledge of poultry business (e.g. when farmers dispose chickens all-year round at mature body weight) and a high degree of managerial ability are two of the most important pre-requisites for a successful business.

The composition of poultry species and other management factors are indicative that most farmers preferred to raise improved/ exotic chickens, and at a small-scale level of production. This suggests that the farmers are low income earners and there is the need to supplement their income in the form of credit loans so as to boost commercial poultry activities to the low income farmers. This income supplementation of the farmers it is expected to bring some improved changes in the management of poultry birds. These changes include regular watering, night enclosures, regularly scheduled vaccinations against common diseases, dietary energy and protein supplementation etc. which can bring significant improvement in the production line of poultry. Such improvements have also been reported under experimental and farm conditions (Bobadoye *et al.*, 2009; Ezema *et al.*, 2009). Sonaiya (1990) reported similar findings in his study on rural poultry production in Africa. However, the rearing method and flock size of birds kept is an indication of good management system employed by most farmers. Chickens and other poultry species that are allowed to scavenge will ultimately lead to insufficient and unbalanced diets, inadequate housing, ill-health and consequently low performance as evident in low egg production or reduced body weight at disposal/ slaughter.

Farmers complained of numerous constraints on poultry production in the area. Feeding cost and disease outbreaks are the major militating factors against efficient production. Disease outbreak encountered by farmers over the last five years included incidences of fowl typhoid, fowl pox, fowl cholera, Gumboro disease, Newcastle disease and coccidiosis as reported by the farmers. These outbreaks mainly occurred during the periods between late wet and late dry seasons (July – March). These seasons coincide with the periods of high amount of rainfall, high relative humidity and harmattan which favour the proliferations of pests and diseases. Sonaiya (1999) reported that poultry development requires a combination of improvement in vaccination, feeding, housing, breeding and farmers' training. Similarly, Smith (1990) suggested that the principal causes of mortality are predators and diseases. Other constraints mentioned include cost of drugs/ medications, weather conditions, inadequate capital, credit facility, veterinary personnel, irregular electricity supply, among others. Training of farmers is essential to successful poultry enterprise, which if regularly carried out will enhance their profit generation and production of quality meat and eggs at reduced cost.

CONCLUSIONS

This study on characterization of poultry farming in the study area revealed that most farmers are operating the business at small scale-level. Increased awareness is required to enlighten the farmers on feed formulation techniques; using locally available feedstuffs so as to reduce the high cost of poultry feeds. However, improved sanitation, regular vaccinations/medications and prompt control of pests and diseases will go a long way towards addressing the recurrent disease outbreaks in the study area.

REFERENCES

Aini, I. (1990). Indigenous chicken production in south-east Asia. *World's Poultry Science Journal*, 46 (1):51-57.

- Bobadoye, A. O., Onibi, G. E., Fajemisin, A. N., Bobadoye, B. O., Okeke, E. N. and Usman, J. M. (2009). Carcass characteristics and muscle development in broiler chickens fed diets containing palm oil sludge in partial replacement for maize. Proceedings of the 34th Annual Conference of Nigerian Society for Animal Production, held between 15th and 18th March, University of Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, pp340- 343.
- Bukar, M. T. (2003). Effect of frequency of ejaculation on semen characteristics in two breeds of turkey (*Meleagris gallopavo*) in a tropical environment. An unpublished B. Agric. Tech. project, Animal Production Programme, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, Nigeria, pp68.
- Butswat, I. S. R., Zahraddeen, D., Mancha, Y. P. and Dachollom, C. C. (2002). Effects of breeds and parity on milk yield of Red Sokoto and Sahel goats. Proceedings of the 7th Annual Conference of Animal Science Association of Nigeria held at the University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Nigeria, September 16 – 19, pp 17-21.
- Ezema, C. Ezejimba, C. C., Eze, D. C. and Kamalu, T. N. (2009). Effects of probiotic (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) on digestibility and growth rate of pullets fed palm kernel cake based diets. Proceedings of the 34th Annual Conference of Nigerian Society for Animal Production, held between 15th and 18th March, University of Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, pp344- 346.
- FAO (1998). Food and Agriculture Organization. Production Year Book, Rome, Italy, pp52.
- FDLPCS (1992). Nigerian Livestock Resources, Vol. 1, Executive Summary and Atlas. A publication of the Federal Department of Livestock and Pest Control Services, Abuja, Nigeria, 30pp.
- Humburg, M.(1977). Statistical Analysis for Decision Making. 2nd Edition, Harcourt Brace, New York, pp801.
- Idi, R.D. (2000). Semen characteristics and fertility of some breeds of cock in Bauchi. Unpublished M. Sc. Thesis, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, Nigeria, pp95.
- Jull, A. A. (1984). Poultry husbandry. Tata McGrawHill, New York, 6th Edition, pp526.
- Kowal, J. M and Knabe, D.T. (1972). Agroclimatological Atlas of the Northern States of Nigeria with explanatory notes. Ahmadu Bello University Press, Zaria, Nigeria, 128p.
- Loveday, R. (1970). A course in statistics. Cambridge University Press, New York, 129pp.
- NPC (2006). National Population Census Figures, National Population Commission, Abuja, Nigeria.
- Obibuaka, L. C. (1983). Agricultural Extension as strategy for agricultural transformation. University of Nigeria Press, Nsukka, Nigeria, pp119.
- Obioha, F.C., (1992). A guide to poultry production in the tropic ACENA Publishers, pp 15--105.
- Oluyemi, J.A. and Roberts F.A. (1988). Poultry production in the warm wet climate. Proceedings of a national seminar on poultry production held at Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria, pp78.
- Sonaiya, E. B. (1999). Rural poultry in Africa. Proceedings of an international workshop, Nigeria, pp 4-6.
- Smith, A. J. (1990). Poultry in the tropical agriculture series. Macmillan publishers, ICTA, 405pp.

TED (1992). Executive diary, Taraba State Government of Nigeria, Jalingo, Taraba State, Nigeria.

Utomakili, J. B. and Inwalowu, O.P. (1993). Socio-economic analysis of farming risks in food crop production in Edo State of Nigeria. A paper presented at the 19th Annual Conference of Farm

Management Association of Nigeria.

Table 1: Socio-economic characteristics and other indices of poultry farming in Taraba State

Item	Frequency	Percentages (%)
<i>Age group (years)</i>		
0 – 20	3	10.7
21 – 40	20	71.4
≥41	5	17.9
<i>Sex</i>		
Male	20	71.4
Female	8	28.6
<i>Educational background</i>		
Primary	0	0.0
Secondary	7	25.0
Tertiary	20	71.4
Qur'anic	1	3.6
Others	0	0.0
<i>Farmers' experience</i>		
1 – 10	23	82.1
11 – 20	3	10.7
21 – 30	1	3.6
31 – 40	1	3.6
<i>Purpose of poultry keeping</i>		
Sale	26	61.9
Consumption	14	33.3
Festival/Religion	0	0.0
Prestige	2	4.8
Manure	0	0.0
Research	0	0.0
Others	0	0.0
<i>Season of disposal/ off-take</i>		
<i>Eid- el- Fitr</i>	6	21.4
<i>Eid-el- Kabir</i>	1	3.6
Easter	1	3.6
Christmas	4	14.3
Wedding/Ceremony	1	3.6
Others	15	53.5

Where the total value within a subset in the frequency column exceeds 28 it is because of multiple choices by the farmers

Table 2: Species composition and other management factors of poultry farming in Taraba State

Item	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Type of poultry		
Chickens	28	87.5
Turkeys	3	9.4
Ostriches	0	0.0
Quails	0	0.0
Guinea fowls	1	3.1
Others	0	0.0
Breed type		
Local	3	10.7
Exotic	25	89.3
Flock size		
≤300	13	46.4
301 – 600	11	39.3
601 - 900	0	0.0
901 – 1200	0	0.0
1201 – 15	4	14.3
≥1501	0	0.0
Management system		
Intensive	24	85.7
Semi-intensive	3	10.7
Extensive	1	3.6

Where the total value within a subset in the frequency column exceeds 28 it is because of multiple choices by the farmers

Table 3: Some constraints of poultry farming in Taraba State, Nigeria

Item	Frequency	Percentages (%)
<i>Disease outbreak in the last five years</i>		
Yes	17	60.7
No	11	39.3
<i>Disease outbreak</i>		
Fowl pox	3	17.6
Fowl cholera	3	17.6
Gumboro	2	11.8
Newcastle	4	23.5
Fowl typhoid	4	23.5
Coccidiosis	1	5.9
<i>Outbreak subjected to confirmatory test</i>		
Yes	18	69.2
No	8	30.8
<i>Season of disease outbreak</i>		
Early dry	8	28.6
Late dry	7	25.0
Early wet	0	0.0
Late wet	13	46.4
<i>Constraints to poultry keeping</i>		
Disease outbreak	13	20.0
Cost of feeds	20	30.8
Cost of drugs/medications	11	16.9
Weather problem	4	6.2
Inadequate capital	5	7.7
Inadequate credit facility	4	6.2
Inadequate veterinary personnel	5	7.7
Irregular electricity supply	3	4.6

Where the total value within a subset in the frequency column exceeds 28 it is because of multiple choices by the farmers

Received for Publication: 22/03/2010

Accepted for Publication: 15/04/2010

Corresponding Author:

D. Zahraddeen

Animal Production Programme, School of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, P.M.B. 0248, Bauchi, Nigeria

E-mail: zdzariya@yahoo.com